

THE BODY AS A SINGLE SELF-DEVELOPING AND SELF-REGULATING BIOLOGICAL SYSTEM

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The development of the organism is carried out in all periods of its life - from the moment of conception to the end of life. This development is called individual, or development in ontogeny. In this case, two periods are distinguished: intrauterine (from the moment of conception to birth) and extrauterine (after birth). Each born person inherits from his parents congenital, genetically determined traits and characteristics that largely determine individual development in the process of his later life. Once after birth, figuratively speaking, in an autonomous mode, the child grows rapidly, the mass, length and surface area of his body increase. Human growth continues until about 20 years of age. Moreover, in girls, the greatest intensity of growth is observed in the period from 10 to 13, and in boys from 12 to 16 years.

An increase in body weight occurs almost in parallel with an increase in its length and stabilizes by 20-25 years. It should be noted that over the past 100 - 150 years in a number of countries there has been an early morphofunctional development of the body in children and adolescents. This phenomenon is called acceleration (lat. *acce1era* - acceleration), it is associated not only with the acceleration of growth and development of the body in general, but also with the earlier onset of puberty, the accelerated development of sensory systems, motor coordination and mental functions.

Therefore, the boundaries between age periods are rather arbitrary and this is due to significant individual differences, in which the "physiological" age and "passport" age do not always coincide. As a rule, adolescence (16 - 21 years) is associated with a period of maturation, when all organs, their systems and apparatus reach their morphological and functional maturity. Mature age (22 - 60 years) is characterized by minor changes in the structure of the body, and the functionality of this rather long period of life is largely determined by the characteristics of lifestyle, nutrition, physical activity. The elderly (61 - 74 years) and senile (75 years and more) are characterized by physiological processes of restructuring, a decrease in the active capabilities of the body and its systems - immune, nervous, circulatory, etc.

A healthy lifestyle, active motor activity in the process of life significantly slow down the aging process. The vital activity of the organism is based on the

process of automatic maintenance of vital factors at the required level, any deviation from which leads to the immediate mobilization of mechanisms that restore this level (homeostasis).

Homeostasis is a set of reactions that ensure the maintenance or restoration of a relatively dynamic constancy of the internal environment and some physiological functions of the human body (blood circulation, metabolism, thermoregulation, etc.). This process is provided by a complex system of coordinated adaptive mechanisms aimed at eliminating or limiting factors that affect the body both from the external and from the internal environment.

They allow you to maintain the constancy of the composition, physico-chemical and biological properties of the internal environment, despite changes in the external world and physiological changes that occur during the life of the organism. In the normal state, fluctuations in physiological and biochemical constants occur within narrow homeostatic boundaries, and the cells of the body live in a relatively constant environment, as they are washed by blood, lymph and tissue fluid. The constancy of the physico-chemical composition is maintained due to the self-regulation of metabolism, blood circulation, digestion, respiration, excretion and other physiological processes. The body is a complex biological system. All his organs are interconnected and interact. Violation of the activity of one organ leads to disruption of the activity of others. A huge number of cells, each of which performs its own functions inherent only to it in the overall structural and functional system of the body, are supplied with nutrients and the necessary amount of oxygen in order to carry out the vital processes of energy generation, excretion of decay products, various biochemical reactions of life, etc. .d. These processes occur due to regulatory mechanisms that operate through the nervous, circulatory, respiratory, endocrine and other systems of the body.

The external environment and its impact on the body and human life.

A person is affected by various environmental factors. When studying the diverse types of its activities, one cannot do without taking into account the influence of natural factors (barometric pressure, gas composition and air humidity, ambient temperature, solar radiation - the so-called physical environment), biological factors of the plant and animal environment, as well as factors of the social environment with the results of everyday, economic, industrial and creative human activities. From the external environment, the body receives substances necessary for its life and development, as well as

irritants (beneficial and harmful), which violate the constancy of the internal environment.

The organism, through the interaction of functional systems, strives in every possible way to maintain the necessary constancy of its internal environment. The activity of all organs and their systems in the whole organism is characterized by certain indicators that have certain ranges of fluctuations. Some constants are stable and rather rigid (for example, blood pH is 7.36 - 7.40, body temperature is in the range of 35 - 42), others normally differ in significant fluctuations (for example, stroke volume of the heart - the amount of blood ejected in one contraction - 50 - 200 cm).

Lower vertebrates, in which the regulation of indicators characterizing the state of the internal environment is imperfect, are at the mercy of environmental factors. For example, a frog, not possessing a mechanism that regulates the constancy of body temperature, duplicates the temperature of the external environment so much that in winter all life processes are slowed down in it, and in summer, being far from water, it dries up and dies. In the process of phylogenetic development, higher animals, including humans, sort of placed themselves in a greenhouse, creating their own stable internal environment and thereby ensuring relative independence from the external environment. Natural and socio-biological factors affecting the human body are inextricably linked with environmental issues.

Ecology (Greek, oikos - house, dwelling, homeland + logos - concept, teaching) is both a field of knowledge, and a part of biology, and an academic discipline, and a complex science. Ecology considers the relationship of organisms with each other and with the non-living components of the nature of the Earth (its biosphere). Human ecology studies the patterns of human interaction with nature, the problems of maintaining and strengthening health. Man depends on the conditions of his environment in the same way that nature depends on man. Meanwhile, the impact of production activities on the environment (pollution of the atmosphere, soil, water bodies with production waste, deforestation, increased radiation as a result of accidents and violations of technology) threatens the existence of man himself. For example, in large cities, the natural habitat is significantly deteriorating, the rhythm of life, the psycho-emotional situation of work, life, rest are disturbed, the climate is changing.

In cities, the intensity of solar radiation is 15–20% lower than in the surrounding area, but the average annual temperature is 1–2 degrees higher, daily and seasonal fluctuations are less significant, atmospheric pressure and

polluted air are lower. All these changes have an extremely adverse effect on the physical and mental health of a person. About 80 diseases of modern man are the result of the deterioration of the ecological situation on the planet. Environmental problems are directly related to the process of organizing and conducting systematic physical exercises and sports, as well as to the conditions in which they occur.

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